

Elevation Analysis of the Ulhas River Basin Using Geospatial Data Classification Methods: A Comparative Study Based on DEM Data

Mr. Devidas Tambe*

Assistant Professor

Department of Geography, University of Mumbai, Mumbai – 400 098. MS India

*Corresponding Author: Devidas Tambe, Email: devidastambe@gmail.com, <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-2269-452X>

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Abstract:

Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) are different types of raster dataset where data classification methods play vital role on terrain and river basin analyses using DEMs. In the present study Ulhas River basin is delineated using SRTM 30-meter spatial resolution DEMs. Further Natural break, Geometric interval, Standard deviation, and Quantile raster data classification methods are employed to understand the elevation characteristics and terrain characteristics in the Ulhas River basin. An author derived classified DEMs with five class intervals with different elevation ranges as per the classification methods. Further area-height histograms were derived all the four-classification method. Also consolidated area statistics matrix is derived. Visual interpretations are derived. From the study it can be concluded that these methods are theoretically different. In spite of this some similarity is observed in standard deviation and natural break method as well as geometric interval and quantile method. That indicates skewed nature of elevation ranges of the Ulhas River basin. The river itself has limited high steep slopes in upstream region and extensive flat undulating regions in the lower reaches. The overall gradient is high in the river and that is exactly reflected in the elevation ranges of the Ulhas River basin. Therefore, one specific method cannot be recommended because the river basin is much skewed in term of elevation characteristics. The selection of the data classification is application specific.

Keywords: Data classification methods, SRTM, Ulhas River, Area statistics matrix and Drainage basin.

1. Introduction

In modern river basin analysis, Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) integral elevation data source in the field of Remote Sensing and Geographical Information Science. There are many open source DEMs data sources. SRTM is one of them which is used in the present study. Classification of DEM data with different elevation ranges is required for various river basin analyses to solve real world problems. There are wide variety of DEM raster data classification method therefore analyst has to select the appropriate classification method from available wide variety of classification methods.

The river is a west flowing river in the vicinity of the city Mumbai. The river has skewed type of elevation characteristics. Therefore, it is verified which method works best on the DEM data for Ulhas River basin to understand the elevation characteristics of the river. The study will draw a conclusion data classification methods and DEM as well as which method works best for Ulhas River basin.

2. Study Area

The river Ulhas River is west flowing river in the vicinity of the city Mumbai. The watershed is having more north south extension. The large escarpment is found in the Eastern side where river originates.

As per the analyses done using SRTM data, the total area of the river basin is 3933 square kilometers. The maximum elevation is 1473 meter which is located in the eastern area of the river basin. The river debouches in the Thane creek. Kalyan and Dombivli are major cities on the Ulhas River. Most of the river basin is covered with low elevation, undulating land surfaces. The figure 1, figure 2, figure 3 and figure 4 shows Ulhas River Basin with classified elevation ranges as per the different raster data classification methods.

3. Research Identification

Following are the major objectives of the present study are, to delineate Ulhas River basin and Ulhas River drainage network with proper threshold values. To apply Natural break, Geometric interval, Standard deviation, and Quantile raster data classification methods on DEM of Ulhas River basin, and to visualize the result. To prepare histogram and consolidated area statistics matrix of elevation ranges and to draw conclusion on data classification methods and Ulhas River elevation characteristics.

4. Literature review

Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) are essential in geomorphic studies. Some of the early works includes Moore et. al, (1991) and Wilson and Gallant (2000). Work also has been done on automatic drainage network detection and watershed boundary detection (Jenson and Domingue, 1988). Availability of SRTM DEM data made the work easier. Farr et. al., (2007) have demonstrated technical detail and applications of SRTM in geomorphology. Meshram and Sharma (2015) have prioritized watershed using SRTM data. Other than extraction of DEMs, delineation of river basins, data classification with various plays vital role in the applications of DEMs. Jenk (1967) have introduce natural junk also known as natural break method for the classification of geographical data. This method is successfully implemented to classify the raster and vector data. According to Brewer and Pickle (2002) quantile method assign equal number of observations to each class but this may damage natural clusters given the dataset. According to Smith et.al (2015) standard deviation data classification method only works if the dataset is normally distributed. The method is based on mean deviation from the mean. Some of the software offers geometric interval data classification method. According to Strahler (1952) hypsometric curve is one of the best methods to understand the elevation in the river basin. This is used to test and analyse the data classification methods suitability in the present study. Willgoose, G. and Hancock, G. (1998) have done some advanced work on elevation distribution and erosion with DEMs. An author con concluded on various data classification methods with applied on area height curve for Ulhas River basin.

5. Datasets:

The Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) covers area between 60 degrees south and 60 degrees north latitude. It is near global radar-based elevation data. In the present study 30-meter spatial resolution SRTM data is used for Ulhas river basin. The dataset is freely available through <https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/> website. This Digital Elevation Model dataset is useful for terrain analysis, watershed analyses, natural hazard studies, 3D visualization, etc. applications.

6. Methodology

Following steps have been employed on SRTM DEMs data in the present dataset.

6.1 Watershed Delineation

The dataset is downloaded from <https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov/> website. Originally the dataset was in WGD 84 geographic projection. It was reprojected in WGS 84-43 North projected coordinate system

to get the areal unit in meter and kilometers. Then the DEM is imported in GRASS Tools in QGIS 3.40.7 software. Further DEM was corrected from pikes, sinks and null values. Further watershed was delineated with threshold value of 1,00,000 pixels. Similarly, drainage network was delineated with threshold values of 50 pixels. Both layers were converted into vector format. Here watershed boundary was exported as polygon. Further Ulhas River drainage network and DEM was clipped with watershed boundary. These watershed boundary, clipped DEM and drainage network was used for data classification, visualization and preparation of maps.

6.2 Raster data classification

There are many kinds of raster data, which includes, remote sensing images, digital elevation models, and thematic raster layers. Thematic raster layers are already classified. Remote sensing images are statistically visualized as histograms but digital elevation models are different and requires specific classification method. In the present study the author has analyzed various data classification method on SRTM DEMs on Ulhas River basin. Total 5 elevation ranges/classes were prepared on the Ulhas River DEM.

7. Results and Discussion

Data classification methods on vector data and raster data is important aspect of geospatial data analysis and map composition. The kind of classification method affect entire data analysis and geospatial visualization. There are specific advantages and disadvantages of each data classification methods. It is essential to do comprehensive study of data classification methods and its impact on data analysis and visualization. We have done analysis on DEMs of the Ulhas River basin which located in the vicinity of the city Mumbai. We have used geometric interval, Natural break, Quantile, and standard deviation data classification methods for the Ulhas River basin using SRTM DEMs data. Following sections give comparative analysis and its interpretation on the total area under the various elevation classes.

7.1 Geometric interval:

The map given in figure 1 is optimised for widely skewed elevation distribution in Ulhas River basin. In this data classification method, the class intervals progress geometrically. Here it can be observed that elevation progressively changes from low elevations to highlands. It highlights terrain transition with elevations. This method is very useful to understand uneven elevation distribution in a river basin.

Figure 1 the drainage basin map is prepared with Geometric interval data classification method.

7.2 Natural break method:

The natural break method given in figure 2 exaggerate difference between classes and reduces the differences within the specified class. It creates the homogeneous classes and separates the dissimilar one. It identifies the actual variation in the elevations. This method is useful to understand the morphometric characteristics of the river basin.

Figure 2 the drainage basin map is prepared with Natural Break data classification method.

7.3 Quantile method:

The quantile data classification method given figure 3 into the equal number of pixels of elevation in different elevation zones. This method does not consider actual elevation range. This method can underestimate or over represent terrain elevations. This is useful for artificial area-based analyses and not for natural characteristics of river basin.

Figure 3 the drainage basin map is prepared with Quantile data classification method.

7.4 Standard Deviation:

The elevation classes given in figure 4 is based on one standard deviation data classification method. This method visualizes how elevation values changes form mean values. This identifies extreme classes of elevations.

Figure 4 the drainage basin map is prepared with Standard deviation data classification method.

Elevation area by Classification Method

The histograms in figure 5 shows elevation classes on as an independent variable and area in square kilometres as dependent variable. There are four histograms in this figure. In this figure standard deviation and natural break data classification methods show wide variation in the area under elevation classes. In standard deviation method lower elevation classes cover large area. Whereas in this method higher elevation areas are very less. On the other hand, natural break method shows uniform decrease in area from lower elevation to higher elevation. The trend is very steep. As the method implies quantile method show uniform distribution in the area under five elevation classes. The geometric interval method suppressed area under lower elevation classes whereas it has enhanced area under higher elevation classes. That is why in geometric interval method there is uniform distribution of area under various elevation classes. In conclusion I can say standard deviation and natural break method have similar shape of histogram with little difference. At the same time geometric interval and quantile have similar shape of histogram with little difference. All four method are different from the perspective of mathematics and statistics but still there are similar pairs of histograms. It suggests that there is self-similarity in the elevation characteristics of the landforms of Ulhas River which has uniform geological and climatological characteristics.

Figure 5 Geometric interval, standard deviation, natural break, and quantile classification method and area under these classification methods in square kilometre.

Consolidated Area Statistics Matrix

The figure 6 shows consolidated area statistics matrix of the Ulhas River basin using geometric interval, natural break, quantile, and standard deviation data classification method. Overall, according to standard deviation the distribution is positively skewed. And that is reflected in natural break and standard deviation data classification method. The same thing can be observed in area consolidated matrix given in figure 6. The extreme can be seen in natural break and standard deviation data classification method. The colour changes are gradual in geometric interval and quantile classification method. The outliers are resulted from natural break and standard deviation data classification method which is absent in geometric interval and quantile data classification method.

Figure 6 Consolidated area statistics matrix of the Ulhas River basin using geometric interval, natural break, quantile, and standard deviation data classification method.

8. Conclusions

From the application of Geometric interval, standard deviation, natural break, and quantile data classification methods on SRTM DEMs data for the Ulhas River basin, it can be concluded that these methods are theoretically different. In spite of this some similarity is observed in standard deviation and natural break method as well as geometric interval and quantile method. That indicates skewed nature of elevation ranges of the Ulhas River basin. The river itself has limited high steep slopes in upstream region and extensive flat undulating regions in the lower reaches. The overall gradient is high in the river and that is exactly reflected in the elevation ranges of the Ulhas River basin. The application of the specific data classification method would be application dependent. For land use palling quantile will be suitable. For landform analyses natural break method will be suitable. For geomorphic processes geometric interval method will be suitable and for statistical understanding of the land surface the standard deviation method will be vary suitable. Therefore, one specific method cannot be recommended because the river basin is much skewed in term of elevation characteristics.

9. References:

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